

JANE AUSTIN

Haydarova Zarina Faxriddin qizi

Shakhrisabz State Pedagogical Institute

3 nd Level Student in the Faculty of “Languages”

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Abstract. This article covers Jane Austen's complete life and work. General information about what happened from his birth to the end of his life, what he did and what books he created in the way of his work. Through this article, you can find answers to any questions you may have about the writer's life and work.

Key words: Hollywood, theatre, novels, published, work, creativity, died, famous, official work.

ДЖЕЙН ОСТИН

Аннотация. В этой статье рассказывается о жизни и творчестве Джейн Остин. Общие сведения о том, что происходило с его рождением до конца жизни, чем он занимался и какие книги создал на пути своего творчества. В этой статье вы найдете ответы на любые вопросы о жизни и творчестве писателя.

Ключевые слова: Голливуд, театр, романы, изданные, произведение, творчество, умер, знаменитость, официальное произведение.

*The more I can of the world
the more I am convinced that
I shall never see a man whom
I can really love...*

There are many talented scientists and writers in the world. One of them is Jane Austen. The famous writer was born on December 18, 1775 in Steventon, Hampshire, England, in a noble family (his father was a rector of the Anglican Church) and was the youngest of 8 children. His father was George Austin and her mother was Cassandra Lay. They had 6 sons and 2 daughters. Her father met his wife Cassandra Lay while studying at Oxford University.

Jane Austen's family was very interested in theater and creativity. When she was young, she and her family organized a play and invited close friends to watch. She was very close to his family, but she and her brother Henry Austin got on with very well.

Jane Austen received her first education at home, and in 1785, the Austen family sent their daughters to Reading Abbey Girls School in order to give them a proper education. But in 1785, due to the increased expenses of their father, they are forced to leave the school. Such events cause a radical change in Jane Austen's life.

The many difficulties she faced in her life make him pick up a pen. Jane Austen started writing to work at the age of 11. But many believe that she started writing novels at the age of 14. Jane Austen wrote under the pseudonym "Juvenilia" from 1787 to 1793. In 1793-1794, Jane Austen wrote a novel called "Lady Susan". Despite the fact that this work was not published for 10 years after his death, it is considered his first official work. Later, one of his novels starts to be written and it is out of print.

- "Sense and Sensibility" in 1811
- "Pride and Prejudice" in 1813

- "Monsfield Park" in 1814
- "Emma" in 1815

And under the pseudonym Juvenilia:

Fredric & Efrida, Harry & Eliza, Jack & Alice ,Edgor & Emma.

Jane Austen's brother's contribution and support in the release of her works was very important. Henry who Jane's brother introduced him to a famous publisher named Thomas Egerton to publish his books. Through his acquaintance, the novel "Sens and Sensibility" will be published. Born and raised in the Pacific Ocean, Austin spent a lot of time attending various events and plays at the Gallery. During these times, she devoted her writing to writing about London life.

Jane Austen had a series of losses throughout her life. In addition, the writer had a lot of love affairs. But despite this, he did not remarry. But in 1802, at the age of 27, she received a marriage proposal from Hanis Bigg-Wither. but this offer will be rejected after 1 day. After these events, Jane Austin decides to take a vacation.

Now the works he gave to each publisher were out of print. And the works she wrote began to be awarded with awards. In particular, his work "Pride and Prejudice" was awarded with famous awards in 1813. Even Lord Byron's wife praised this work. And this work is sold in several editions around the world. In addition, this work was made into a movie. Famous Hollywood actors and actresses such as Keira Knightley, Matthew McFadden, Rosamund Pike played roles in the movie. This movie was nominated for Oscar 10 times. In addition, the heroes of Austin's main works, like himself, did not seek marriage as the greatest achievement in their lives. They just believed in true love and lived.

After that, in 1814, "Emma", which was the most worked on of all her works, was published. But it did not mention Jane's name. She describes this situation as "I don't look like anyone else but myself."

Jane Austen devoted almost her entire life to writing. And after that, she gets some achievements and popularity. Unfortunately, she died on July 18, 1817 in Wenches-Terold and was buried there on July 24. Some sources say that Austin died of poisoning, while others say that she died of a serious illness. She is the author of many books about the nobility, the author of the best works of English fiction. Janet Austen's 249th birthday will be celebrated on December 16, 2023.

In conclusion, more than 200 centuries have passed since her creation, and her works are still immortal. And we young people should study her work and enjoy her immortal works. And by reading her works, we should recognize and follow her example as a true writer.

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